

1 **Padi4 is expressed in the natural killer cell and perturbed in chronic autoimmune and inflammatory**
2 **disease.**

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8 We describe here PADI4 as a component gene of the natural killer gene and its dysregulation in
9 autoimmune and inflammatory disease. PADI4 expression defined the killer cell progenitor. PADI4
10 expression was a partial function of KIR2DL3 expression in immune cells. Padi4 expression was
11 perturbed in multiple autoimmune and inflammatory contexts: activated in polymorphonuclear cells from
12 humans with chronic granulomatous disease (CGD) during infection, silenced in the Tfh cell in humans
13 with MS, and activated in primary monocytes from humans with Crohn's Disease.
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